

AZINE DYES DERIVED FROM 9:10-PHENANTHRATHIOPHENE-2':3'-DIONE.

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Azine dyes derived from 9-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione have been described.

9-Phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione, prepared from 9-thiolphenanthrene (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 469), has been condensed with various *ortho*-diamines such as *o*-phenylenediamine, 2-chloro-4:5-toluenediamine, 2:3-diaminoquinoxalin, and 2:3-diaminophenazine and thereby the corresponding azines obtained. As has already been observed, the colour of these azine dyes deepens as the number of azine rings in the molecule increases. A further communication will describe the indigoid dyes derived from 9-thiolphenanthrene as well as 9-phenanthrathiophen-2':3'-dione. The work is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

9:10-Phenanthrathiophene-phenazine (I, R = R₁ = H).

o-Phenylenediamine (2 g.) was added to a solution of 9-phenanthrathiophene 2':3'-dione (I) (0.5 g.) in acetic acid (50 c.c.) and the solution shaken. The colour of the solution immediately became lighter and a yellow substance in the form of needles separated out. The mixture was boiled for 15 minutes more and filtered hot, the crystals washed with acetic acid and finally with water. The substance was then recrystallised from pyridine in yellow, slender shining needles, m. p. 255°. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a green colour. (Found: N, 8.21. C₂₂H₁₂N₂S requires N, 8.33 per cent).

9:10-Phenanthrathiophene-2'-chloro-4':5'-tolazine (I, R = Me; R₁ = Cl) was prepared in a similar way as the previous compound from 9-phenanthrathiophene-2':3'-dione (0.5 g.) and 2-chloro-4:5-toluenediamine (0.3 g.):

It was recrystallised from pyridine in yellow fine needles which shrink at 265° and melt at 271° . The compound dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a blue colour. (Found : N, 7.02. $C_{22}H_{13}N_2ClS$ requires N, 7.28 per cent).

Quinoxaline-9 : 10-phenanthrathiophneazine..

It was prepared from 9-phenanthrathiophene-2' : 3'-dione (0.3 g.) and 2 : 3-diaminoquinoxalin (0.15 g.) in acetic acid solution by boiling for 2 hours. The solution was diluted, warmed and the brownish red precipitate collected. This was washed with dilute acetic acid and hot water and recrystallised from pyridine with the addition of hot water as a red crystalline mass, m. p. 233° - 34° . It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a violet colour. (Found : N, 14.14. $C_{24}H_{13}N_4S$ requires N, 14.43 per cent).

9 : 10-Phenanthrathiophene-phenazineine,

It was prepared from 9-phenanthrathiophene-2 : 3'-dione (0.3 g.) and diaminophenazine (0.2 g.) in acetic acid solution by heating for 2 hours. The red solution during the process gradually became dark red and dark chocolate precipitate separated out. It was filtered and the precipitate washed with acetic acid and water. The dark-coloured precipitate was recrystallised from pyridine as a chocolate crystalline mass melting above 290° . It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a bluish black colour. (Found : N, 12.53. $C_{28}H_{14}N_4S$ requires N, 12.78 per cent).